

THEORETICAL BASIS OF LINGUISTIC FEATURES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE METHODOLOGY

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Annotation: *The peculiarity of the translation is that, despite the fact that necessary changes are made to the original text, it is accepted as a full-fledged replacement of the original. This article identified the types of translation equivalence, adequacy and adequate translation.*

Keywords: *translation, language, equivalent, adequate*

“Any language expresses to the extent that it is necessary for a society that is a means of communication. Any phonetics can be expressed with the help of any phonetics, anything,” complements the idea of Sapir Meillet [Ortega y Gasset 1991 : 529]. At the same time, this potential opportunity to express everything does not always exist in a particular language, which is exactly why it is difficult to make a full-fledged translation in all respects.

It should be noted that the main difficulty associated with the formation of the concept of equivalence is primarily related to the multi-level and heterogeneity of this concept, which is associated with the semantic, structural, functional, communicative, pragmatic, genre and other characteristics. All the above parameters should be kept in translation. Artwork also varies in terms and methods of translation, the degree of their implementation in the field [Vinogradov 2001]. Several types of equivalence in works related to the theory of translation: “functional equivalence”, “stylistic equivalence”, “formal equivalence”, “text equivalence”, “communicative equivalence”, “linguistic equivalence”, “pragmatic equivalence”, “semantic equivalence”, “dynamic equivalence”, “ontological equivalence” equivalence can be listed as “etc. [Gorli 1994: 170].

In order to understand the concept of translation equivalence, it is necessary, first of all, to comprehensively consider the different approaches to interpretation of the structure of equivalence.

Many researchers devoted their work to this problem. This section presents the most valid and time-tested theories.

V.N. Komissarov in his book "Theory of translation (linguistic aspects)" [Komissarov 1990] developed a theory of equivalence levels, according to which in the translation process, an equivalence relationship is established between the corresponding levels of originality and translation. V.N.Komissarov identified five levels of content in terms of originality and content of the translation:

1. Communication objective level;
2. Degree of description of the situation;
3. Statement level;
4. Information level;
5. Level of language signs.

V.N. According to Komissarov's theory, the translation equivalence is the maximum equality of all levels of the content of originals and translated texts. Artwork and translation units can be all five levels or just some equivalent to each other. Both the original and the translated language can be full equivalents, equivalent units or contextual equivalents, similar to each other. At the same time, their correct assessment, selection, selection and application depend on the skill of the translator, his knowledge, skills and creativity, the ability to take into account and compare the entire complex of linguistic and extralinguistic factors. In the process of translation, each translator solves a difficult task: it is necessary not only to find and choose the required equivalent unit, but also to use it correctly, to create communicative equivalent information in two languages.

Komissarov divides both types of equivalence. The first is the potential achievable equivalence, and the maximum is the totality of the unit of content of the texts in the two languages that are created close to each other; taking into account the structural differences in the languages in which these texts are created; you can call this equivalence ideal or theoretical. The second is the practical, translation equivalence, that is, the original and the real semantic proximity of the translated texts, which the translator achieved during the translation process. Accordingly, in the process of translation, the translator, proceeding from a certain text, approaches the translation in different ways to the original, achieves a different degree of preservation and closeness of the content, thereby striving for and achieving a potentially achievable equivalent.

Variations in the original language and instruction language systems, and the peculiarities of creating text in each of these languages, to a different extent, can limit the possibility of fully preserving the content of

the original in translation. Therefore, the translation equivalence can be based on the preservation (and, accordingly, the loss) of the various elements of meaning that exist in the original. To ensure its equivalence in translation, different degrees (types) of equivalence are distinguished, depending on which part of the content is transferred. But the main thing is that at any level of equivalence the translation language can provide communication.

In conclusion, we can say that although there is no clear and complete definition of the concept of "equivalence", many definitions are given either by descriptive or by denial. Nevertheless, if we try to summarize all of the above, then the main essence of the concept of translation equivalence can be determined by the equivalence of the content, the equality of information. More attention in interpreting this concept is paid to the preservation and transmission of the original content plan in translation. Based on this, we understand that equivalence is the most complete semantic similarity between the maximum attainable content generality as well as the original and translation.

In the early period of its development as a translation science, its two methods were distinguished. The first is a direct translation of the mountain, indicating a literal translation of the original. The second method, aimed at delivering pure content of the artwork by any means or in any way, was considered a free translation. Later, by the XVIII century, the direction of the translation based on turning the original in accordance with its norms and requirements of classicism came to the square [Kryukov 1989: 9]. Since the XIX century, the term "exact translation" has often been used in the meaning of "correctly translated". Later, in the XX century, the terms "literally" and "xijjavi" appeared. At the same time, instead of the previously used term "exact translation", the term "adequate translation", that is, the term "absolute equivalent translation", appeared. Under the term "adequate translation", the meaning of "accurate, accurate, qualitative translation" is understood. G.R.Gachechiladze writes in his work "artistic translation and literary relations": "artistic translation is a vibration between two extreme principles: literal, but artistically imperfect translation and artistic precision, but far from the original, free translation" [Gachechiladze 1980: 81]. In the artistic sense, the "adequate" translation may not be adequate in relation to linguistics, its individual elements. 87-88].

With the development of the theory of translation, other interpretations of the concept of "adequate translation" naturally began to

appear. Some of them did not give a sufficiently clear definition to the concept, which led to terminological uncertainty. Such definitions can be attributed to the following: "adequate translation is the re-creation of the content and form unity of the original in another language tool. Adequate translation-the main goal of artistic translation"[Minyar-Beloruhev 1980: 221]. Such a definition is general and mavhum, and does not reflect the specific features of the concept of "adequate".

A.V.Fedorov used the term "adequate" in a different interpretation, using it in the sense of "full-fledged, semantic and stylistically equivalent" [Fedorov 1983: 127].

I.I.Revzin and V.No, it's not. And the rosenzweigs put more stringent requirements. They considered that the concepts "xijavi", "adequate" and "free" in scientific theory can not be supported at all and should be replaced by other more accurate terms. The above terms can only be applied to poetics. Bunda, they have, on the one hand, taken into account that "on the other hand, artistic and aesthetic phenomena" refer to "linguistic phenomena (artistry (AT) translation of language (TT), in which those or those elements are mutually compatible or inconsistent) [Revzin, Rosenzweig 1964: 121].

The above terminology and conjectural ambiguity sometimes also led to such categorical opinions as: "adekvatlik (full and correct translation) can not be an obligatory condition of translation" [Minyar-Beloruhev 1976: 21] or "the concept of maintaining integrity in written translation is not a necessary condition" [Kazakova 1988: 6]. Such thoughts can not be called correct, because they undermine the approach and attention to the concept of "adekvatlik". Failure to adequately turn over the artwork undermines its semantic and stylistic aspects. Also, the implementation of the translation without a holistic understanding of the whole original will lead to separate parts of the original and, in general, a violation of the original text and unreasonable changes. Also, the implementation of the translation without a complete understanding of the original leads to a violation and unreasonable changes in both individual parts of the original and the translated text in general.

Above, the basic concepts of the theory of translation, such as "adequacy" and "equivalence", were considered. However, until now, the question of the relationship between these two concepts has not been raised.

This problem has not yet found a clear solution, and in the next place it was tried to look at the various points of view expressed about them.

The term "adequate", which appeared earlier than the term "equivalent", was originally used as its synonym. Subsequently, the concept of "adequate" began to be used in a broader sense as a term denoting "good", "full", and "equivalent" as a narrower term denoting the semantic generality of the original and translation. A complete scientific description of the differences between these terms and the concepts indicated by A.D. Schweitzer gave: "if the equivalence answers the question of whether the final text corresponds to the original or not, the adekvatlik answers the question of whether the translation, as a process, meets the given communicative conditions. "[Schweitzer 1988: 95]. "Adequate" means "the most optimal in a given communication environment". The translation concludes that the secondary text can be adequate even if it is equivalent to the original only in one of the semiotic levels or in one of the functional dimensions, the scientist concluded. [There: 96]. Accordingly, A. Schweitzer believes that equivalence and adexity are not synonymous because adexity determines the quality of the translation solution as a process, while equivalence is the ratio of the resulting original and translated texts [Schweitzer 1988]. Nevertheless, the terms "adequate" and "equivalent" are used in all the above meanings, including both in translation practice and in scientific literature, as a synonym

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